

THE ROLE OF NUTRITIONAL THERAPY IN THE RECOVERY OF CHILDREN AFTER CARDIAC SURGERY

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Abstract. *Background:* Congenital heart defects in children often require surgical correction during early infancy. Postoperative recovery is significantly influenced by timely and individualized nutritional support. *Objective:* To evaluate the effectiveness of individualized nutritional therapy during the early postoperative period in children after cardiac surgery and its impact on clinical outcomes, recovery duration, and the incidence of postoperative complications. *Methods:* This prospective study included 80 pediatric patients aged 2 months to 5 years who underwent open-heart surgery with cardiopulmonary bypass. Patients were divided into two groups: a control group receiving standard nutritional support and an intervention group receiving individualized nutritional therapy according to ESPEN (2020) and ASPEN (2017) guidelines. Anthropometric measurements, laboratory parameters, length of stay in the intensive care unit (ICU) and hospital, and postoperative complications were assessed. *Results:* Patients in the intervention group demonstrated significantly improved nutritional status, higher levels of albumin and prealbumin, lower C-reactive protein (CRP) levels, and better hematological profiles. The intervention group showed a 35% reduction in ICU stay duration and a significant decrease in total hospitalization time and the rate of postoperative complications compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). *Conclusions:* Early initiation of individualized, nutrient-enriched nutritional therapy after cardiac surgery promotes faster recovery, reduces inflammatory responses, shortens ICU and hospital stays, and decreases the incidence of postoperative complications in pediatric patients. Personalized nutritional strategies are critical for optimizing postoperative outcomes in this vulnerable population.

Keywords: *pediatric cardiac surgery; nutritional support; early postoperative nutrition; congenital heart defects; clinical outcomes; protein-energy malnutrition; intensive care.*

Introduction. Recent advances in pediatric cardiac surgery have enabled the correction of severe congenital heart defects in young children. However, the success of surgical interventions largely depends on the timely initiation and proper organization of nutritional therapy [1, 4, 6]. Effective nutritional support is a critical factor in reducing the risk of postoperative complications, improving clinical outcomes, and shortening the duration of stay in pediatric intensive care units [5, 8].

The organization of nutritional therapy for children with congenital heart defects in the early postoperative period is of particular importance, as the high levels of stress and catabolic responses demand adequate energy and nutrient intake [3, 7, 10]. According to research, early initiation of high-energy nutrition improves postoperative recovery in infants following cardiac surgery, promoting the rapid stabilization of metabolic processes [4, 10].

The 2023 expert consensus highlights the necessity of a specialized approach to nutritional support for children following cardiac surgery, taking into account the specific features of

metabolism and energy expenditure, which directly influence the rate of recovery [9]. An analysis of nutritional status conducted across various countries confirms the importance of adequately assessing nutrition both before and after cardiac surgical interventions to prevent adverse clinical outcomes and organ dysfunction [6, 11, 12].

The authors emphasize the need for a comprehensive approach to nutritional support in children with surgical pathology complicated by severe protein-energy malnutrition [1, 2, 3]. According to their studies, the timely initiation of nutritional therapy significantly improves recovery outcomes and reduces mortality among critically ill pediatric patients [2, 3].

Despite the widespread recognition of the importance of nutritional therapy in global pediatric practice, clinical settings still often demonstrate insufficient attention to the provision of adequate nutritional support for children following cardiac surgery. This highlights the relevance of further research and optimization of nutritional strategies [13, 14].

Objective of the study— to evaluate the effectiveness of nutritional therapy in the early postoperative period in children after cardiac surgery and to determine its impact on clinical outcomes, recovery time, and the incidence of postoperative complications.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted in the cardiac intensive care unit of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. Children aged from 2 months to 5 years who underwent surgery for the correction of congenital heart defects of varying complexity during the period from 2023 to 2024 were included in the study.

Inclusion criteria:

- age of patients from 2 months to 5 years;
- undergoing open-heart surgery with cardiopulmonary bypass;
- availability of informed consent from the parents or legal guardians for the child's participation in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

- presence of severe concomitant developmental anomalies unrelated to cardiovascular pathology;
- syndromic diseases or severe neurological disorders preventing the objective assessment of nutritional status and postoperative recovery;
- refusal of parents to allow the child's participation in the study.

Patients in the control group received standard nutritional support: enteral nutrition was initiated on postoperative days 2–3; the caloric intake was 85–100 kcal/kg/day for children under one year and 80–90 kcal/kg/day for children older than one year; protein intake was maintained at 1.5–2.0 g/kg/day. Standard polymeric formulas (1.0 kcal/mL) without specialized additives were used. If enteral nutrition was not feasible, standard parenteral nutrition was administered.

Patients in the intervention group received individualized nutritional therapy according to the ESPEN (2020) and ASPEN (2017) guidelines, with feeding initiated 6–12 hours after surgery. Caloric intake was calculated using the Schofield equation adjusted for a stress factor: 100–120 kcal/kg/day for children under one year and 90–110 kcal/kg/day for children over one year. Protein intake ranged from 2.5 to 3.0 g/kg/day. Specialized formulas enriched with glutamine, arginine, omega-3 fatty acids, and micronutrients (zinc, selenium, vitamins B, C, and A) were used.

To assess the effectiveness of nutritional therapy, the following methods and indicators were applied:

- anthropometric evaluation (body weight, height, body mass index, mid-upper arm circumference, and skinfold thickness);
- laboratory monitoring of nutritional and metabolic parameters (total protein, albumin, prealbumin, transferrin, glucose, and electrolyte levels);
- monitoring the duration of stay in the cardiac intensive care unit and total hospitalization period;
- assessment of the incidence of postoperative complications (infections, respiratory complications, wound healing disorders, multiple organ dysfunction).

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS Statistics version 26.0. The significance of differences between the groups was assessed using Student's t-test for quantitative data and the chi-square (χ^2) test for qualitative data. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. The study was conducted in accordance with all ethical standards and was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Center. Informed consent for participation was obtained from the parents of all enrolled children.

Results. A total of 80 children were included in the study, with patients evenly distributed into two groups of 40 each. The gender distribution was comparable between the groups: in the control group, boys accounted for 55% and girls for 45%, whereas in the intervention group, boys constituted 52.5% and girls 47.5%. The mean age of patients was 18.2 months in the control group and 17.8 months in the intervention group, indicating similar age characteristics between the groups. No statistically significant differences were observed in physical parameters: the mean body weight in the control group was 8.9 kg, compared to 9.1 kg in the intervention group; mean height was 73.4 cm and 74.2 cm, respectively. Thus, both groups were comparable in terms of key demographic and physical characteristics, ensuring the validity of comparing the effectiveness of the nutritional therapies administered.

Figure 1. Main laboratory parameters in patients of both groups

Children in the intervention group showed a statistically significant improvement in nutritional status as early as 5–7 days after surgery. The presented diagram (Figure 1) illustrates the main laboratory parameters in both groups, clearly demonstrating the effectiveness of individualized nutritional therapy in children after cardiac surgery. The most pronounced

differences between groups were observed in albumin and prealbumin levels: in the intervention group, albumin levels were 36.2 g/L and prealbumin levels were 0.28 g/L, significantly higher compared to the control group (32.5 g/L and 0.22 g/L, respectively). A notable improvement was also identified in C-reactive protein (CRP) levels, which were significantly lower in children receiving specialized nutritional support (9.8 mg/L) compared to the control group (22.0 mg/L), indicating a reduction in inflammatory response.

Glucose levels in the intervention group remained stable and within normal ranges (5.2 mmol/L compared to 5.8 mmol/L in the control group). Hematological parameters also indicated the benefits of individualized nutritional therapy: hemoglobin levels were higher in the intervention group (112 g/L versus 105 g/L in the control group), while leukocyte counts were lower ($10.5 \times 10^9/L$ compared to $14.1 \times 10^9/L$), reflecting a lower degree of inflammation and better overall physiological adaptation.

Figure 2. Study endpoints

The average length of stay in the cardiac intensive care unit for patients in the intervention group was 4.1 ± 1.2 days, compared to 6.3 ± 1.8 days in the control group ($p < 0.01$). Patients receiving specialized nutritional support demonstrated faster recovery, allowing a reduction in intensive care unit stay by nearly 35% (Figure 2). The overall length of hospital stay was also shorter in the intervention group (9.7 ± 2.3 days versus 12.5 ± 2.9 days in the control group, $p < 0.05$).

Thanks to the improvement in metabolic status and a decrease in the frequency of complications, the intervention group achieved a significant reduction in the total duration of hospitalization.

The incidence of postoperative complications (including infections, delayed wound healing, and episodes of multiple organ dysfunction) was also significantly lower in the intervention group: 12.5% compared to 32.5% in the control group ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion. The data obtained confirm the critical role of nutritional therapy in the postoperative recovery of children with congenital heart defects. The analysis demonstrated that an individualized approach to nutritional support during the early postoperative period significantly improves both clinical and laboratory parameters.

The reduction in the duration of stay in the intensive care unit and overall hospitalization, along with the decreased incidence of postoperative complications in the intervention group, indicates the high clinical effectiveness of early high-energy nutrition tailored to the metabolic needs of the child. These results are consistent with findings from other studies emphasizing the benefits of early nutritional intervention under conditions of metabolic stress and catabolism [12, 13].

Improvements in laboratory parameters — including increased levels of albumin and prealbumin, decreased C-reactive protein levels, and normalization of hematological indices — reflect a more stable nutritional and metabolic status in patients who received specialized nutrient-enriched formulas. In particular, glutamine and arginine play important roles in maintaining intestinal barrier function, supporting immune responses, and promoting tissue healing, whereas omega-3 fatty acids exhibit strong anti-inflammatory effects.

Conclusion. The findings of this study highlight the need to revise standard nutritional support protocols toward earlier initiation of feeding and the use of nutrient-enriched formulas. At the same time, it is essential to consider the individual needs of each patient, ensuring a proper balance between volume, composition, and the tolerability of nutritional therapy.

Thus, the implementation of personalized nutritional support for children following cardiac surgery contributes to accelerated recovery, reduced risk of complications, and enhanced effectiveness of intensive care.

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